

SCOPE OF AYURVEDA IN COSMETOLOGY: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Cosmetology combines art and science to improve appearance and boost self-esteem. The desire for beautiful skin has led to increased experimentation with cosmetic items. Unfortunately, many goods in this category include dangerous substances that might cause health concerns. *Ayurveda* takes a comprehensive approach, using natural herbs to detoxify the body from inside. The traditional philosophy of nurturing the body, mind, and spirit has gained popularity in cosmetology for its unique approach to beauty and safe beauty treatments. Skin health is directly linked to mental well-being, and stress can significantly impact skin condition. *Ayurveda* emphasises stress reduction through techniques such as *yoga* and *pranayama*. Following^[1] *Rithucharya*,^[2] *Dinacharya*, and^[3] *Pathya Ahara Vihara* improves metabolism and skin health. *Ayurvedic* scriptures propose using drugs such *Varnya*, *Kustaghna*, *Vayasthapak mahakashayas*, and *Eladi gana*, as well as medicinal plants including *Haridra*, *Manjistha*, *Chandana*, *Amalaki*, and *Bhringaraj*, to improve skin and hair health and prevent ageing. *Ayurvedic* medicine include *Shodhana Chikitsa*, which eliminates^[4] *Ama* and *Bahu doshas*, and^[5] *Samana Chikitsa*, which balances the *Tridoshas*, *Agni*, and^[6] *Sapthadhathus*.

KEYWORDS: *Rithucharya*, *Dinacharya*, and *Pathya Ahara Vihara*, *Ama*, *Samana Chikitsa*, *Sapthadhathus*.

INTRODUCTION

Beauty is a divine gift that humanity has treasured and enjoyed throughout history. People have always sought ways to preserve and enhance beauty in many ways. *Ayurveda*, an ancient system of indigenous medicine, is unique in that it combines medical science with the art of living. It goes beyond the superficial qualities of skin and hair to show a healthy body and mind. Beauty is a comprehensive notion in *Ayurveda* that encompasses the mind, body, and soul, and is regarded as a fundamental component of an individual's individuality. Since the Vedic period in India, there has been a strong emphasis on various therapies and ways for boosting beauty and charm.

Ayurveda is becoming increasingly popular in cosmetology because to its unique approach to beauty and its effective, inexpensive, and long-lasting treatments with little side effects. Over the last decade, there has been a renewed interest in natural and organic beauty treatments, resulting in a renaissance in the popularity of *Ayurvedic* formulas. Cosmetologists can use *Ayurvedic* expertise to produce treatments that address not only superficial beauty concerns but also boost general wellness. This collaboration creates unique chances for specialists in both fields, stimulating the development of goods that are functional, safe, and adhere to sustainable norms. The basis of beauty in *Ayurveda* is laid even before birth, affected by *Dinacharya*, *Ratricharya*, and *Ritucharya* (daily,

nocturnal, and seasonal regimens), as well as the usage of therapeutic herbs and minerals. According to Acharya Vagbhata, the skin tone of the embryo is determined by the mother's food (*Ahara*) and lifestyle (*Vihara*). The skin is recognised as a major maternal feature passed down from mother to kid. Acharyas classified many plants according to their beauty effects, such as *Varnya*, *Keshya*, and so on. Furthermore, *Sushruta* is regarded as a pioneer in the development of notions such as plastic surgery, which includes treatments like auroplasty and rhinoplasty. We live in an era where cosmetology, cosmetic and reconstructive surgery, and aesthetic operations are popular, motivating various production and marketing organisations globally to focus on this industry. India, as one of the largest marketplaces, is very appealing to these businesses. Cosmetics have become an essential part of daily life, but synthetic chemicals can cause a variety of side effects, including systemic responses, allergies, skin and mucous membrane irritation, photo-irritation, and photoallergy. This has sparked renewed interest in herbal cosmetics, with Ayurvedic beauty products rapidly replacing chemical equivalents. Ayurveda, often known as the science of life, offers a comprehensive approach to cosmetic science that addresses both preventive and enhancing aspects of beauty, as well as treating beauty-related illnesses. Ayurvedic natural cosmetics in India have the potential to significantly boost the economy.

OBJECTIVES

To examine the scope of Cosmetology in *Ayurveda*.

To explore the beneficial effect of cosmetology on a healthy lifestyle using *Ayurveda*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The sources of information include different Samhitas, periodicals, and the internet, which required a thorough search for pertinent studies on PubMed and Google Scholar.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

ROLE OF DINACHARYA

Dinacharya describes the everyday actions suggested by Ayurveda for living a healthy, disease-free lifestyle. These practices aid digestion, absorption, and assimilation while also supporting longevity and regulating biological rhythms. The Dinacharya Adhyaya describes a variety of techniques that improve an individual's beauty.

- *Abhyanga*, or massage, softens the body, nourishes the tissues (*Dhatus*), and boosts skin strength, brightness, and complexion. It improves skin texture and contributes to an attractive appearance.
- *Shiroabhyanga*, or head massage, makes hair longer, shinier, and darker while also smoothing it. Furthermore, it improves face beauty, prevents baldness (*Khalitya*) and premature greying (*Palitya*), strengthens hair roots, and promotes the growth of long, black hair.

- *Pāda Abhyanga*, or foot massage, softens the skin on the soles and reduces roughness, dryness, and numbness. It prevents cracking and improves the suppleness, strength, and firmness of the foot.
- *Vyayama*, or exercise, is critical for overall health and radiant attractiveness. It opens the body's pathways, ensuring that tissues are properly nourished and cleansed via sweat and other methods. Exercise also strengthens the muscles and increases physical firmness. On a mental and emotional level, it relieves tension and anxiety, promoting overall well-being and leading to deep, peaceful sleep.
- *Snana*, or bathing, is good for increasing *Ojas*, which boosts vigour and vitality.
- *Dhoompana*, or fumigation, strengthens the hair, skull, sensory organs, and voice.
- *Mukha prakshālana*, or face washing, can alleviate facial dryness (*Mukhashosha*), boils (*Pidaka*), blue spots (*Nilika*), and freckles (*Vyanga*).
- *Gandusha*, or gargling, helps to remove unwanted odours and tastes from the tongue. It revitalises teeth and gums, brightens the face, and prevents tooth decay, sensitivity, and chapped lips.
- *Anjana*, particularly *Sauviranjana* (antimony), should be used on a daily basis, but *Rasanjana* (derived from *Berberis aristata*) can be used every five to eight days. This practice is beneficial to the eyes, as it lowers excess kapha while also strengthening and brightening eyelashes.
- *Udvaratana*, or powder massage, aids in fat loss (*Medas*), improves skin complexion, strengthens the body, eliminates undesirable smells, and relieves itching.
- *Utsādana* (massage with greasy paste) and *Udgharshana* (massage with dry powders) promote skin radiance by improving blood circulation. *Utsādana*, particularly for ladies, enhances skin lustre and encourages positivity and cleanliness. These activities increase vision and give the cheeks and face a lotus-like appearance, as well as treat boils, black moles, freckles, and grey hairs. They also help prevent wrinkles.^[1-4]

A variety of practices that improve life quality are included in *dinacharya*. The health of skin and hair is directly improved by practices like exercise (*Vyayama*), powder massage (*Udwarthanam*), fumigation (*Dhoomapanam*), and particular oil application (*Murdhini taila*).

ROLE OF RITUCHARYA

Ayurvedic literature promotes "*Ritucharya*" to maintain health and beauty throughout the seasons. This practice offers cosmetic recommendations. Applying *Agaru* (*Acquillaria agallocha*) during the cold seasons of *Hemantha* and *Shishira* can protect skin from adverse weather conditions. During *Shishira*, avoid meals and drinks that increase *Vata*, such as pungent, bitter, and astringent. In spring, apply a paste of sandalwood and *Agaru* (*Acquillaria agallocha*) to the body and consume a

diet rich in barley and wheat. During summer, ingesting sweet, cold, watery, and greasy foods and drinks is beneficial. These food and lifestyle routines promote health and attractiveness while defending against extreme weather conditions throughout the year.

AGNI'S ROLE

Agni forms the foundation for both *Prabha* (lustre) and *Varna* (complexion). Maintaining a balanced *Agni*, or *Samagni*, is crucial for a healthy complexion. *Pathyahara* is a balanced diet that can help achieve *Samagni*. A balanced diet aids *Uthorothara Dhathu Poshana* by keeping *Agni* in balance and promoting efficient digestion and assimilation of food. A healthy *Raktha dhathu* promotes vibrant skin and hair.

Skin And Doshas

Skin health and youthfulness are determined by the equilibrium of *Kapha*, which is maintained by Ayurvedic cosmeceuticals. To keep *Kapha* skin healthy, warm oil massage and skin washing are advised. Because the *Pitta*-pacifying products preserve metabolic processes, they regulate the skin's chemical and hormonal responses.

Pitta-dominant skin can be made healthier with the use of sunscreens, skin-protective creams, and face oils, among other products. *Vata* regulates the effective flow of blood and nutrients, therefore items that balance *Vata* aid in skin nourishment. Natural moisturisers and warm oil massages may help restore the health of *Vata* skin.

Skin And Dhatus

- *Rasa Dhatu* maintains the health of the skin and supports bodily tissues; hence, medications that enhance *Rasa Dhatu* enhance skin health.
- Drugs that purify *Rakta* also improve skin health since *Rakta Dhatu* detoxifies the skin and prevents disorders linked to the buildup of toxins.
- *Mamsa Dhatu* keeps the skin stiff and gives it firmness.

All three Dhatus—*Rasa*, *Rakta*, and *Mamsa*—should be enhanced by the Ayurvedic cosmetic to enhance the general health of the skin. Similar to this, Ayurvedic anti-aging treatments *Urjaskara* and *Vyadhihara* operate in two ways: first, as a promotive approach, and then, as a curative therapy.^[13-16]

ROLE OF PATHYAHARA

Pathyahara describes food as nutrient-dense, lighter, easy to Digest and consumed in appropriate quantities. The type and amount of food chosen should be appropriate for an individual's constitution. In *Ayurveda*, good digestion and absorption of food, as well as regular and efficient waste removal, are essential for keeping a balanced, robust, and beautiful body. These ingredients promote good skin, bright eyes, lustrous hair, strong nails, endurance, mental clarity, and a kind, compassionate demeanour.

SAMANA CHIKITSA AND SODHANA'S ROLE

The two main types of treatment in *Ayurveda* are *Shodhana* (purification) and *Shamana* (herbal medication).

SHODHANA CHIKITSA: When the *Doshas* are severely vitiated and the situation is chronic, *Shodhana* Chikitsa should be given initially. *Shodhana* Chikitsas classified as *Panchakarma* include *Basti*, *Vamana*, *Virechan*, *Raktamokshana*, and *Nasya*. *Shodhana* is crucial for detoxifying the body and allowing its natural healing mechanisms to work properly. *Vamana* and *Virechana* karmas are especially effective for treating hair loss, alopecia, and acne. *Basti* is extremely good to skin health, whereas *Nasya* treats pigmented areas on the face and prevents premature ageing, which has an instant positive effect on hair concerns. *Ayurvedic* oil taken through the nose promotes hair renewal. *Jalouka* (leech therapy) is efficient at breaking down blood clots and improving circulation, which improves hair follicles and stimulates hair growth in bald areas. This therapy also promotes wound healing and acne treatment. *Shashtika Shali Pinda Swedana* is crucial for skin care and beauty, as it is nourishing, heavy, stable, cooling, and balancing for all *doshas*. It improves complexion and increases blood flow to the face, which helps with conditions like *Vyanga* (blemish), *Nyachha*, and *Tilakalaka* (non-elevated mole), as well as washing and revitalising the facial skin. *Shirobasti*, which retains hot medicated oil on the head, and *Shirodhara*, which pours oil over the head, can help preserve hair health. These therapies are excellent for treating hair loss, alopecia, and renewing dry follicles.

SHAMANA CHIKITSA

When the *Doshas* are balanced and the body is weak, *Shamana* Chikitsa is more effective. This treatment includes both internal and exterior approaches. Internal treatment entails consuming proper foods and pharmaceuticals, while external treatment involves applying medicinal oils, ointments, and other therapies. *Ayurvedic* medicine suggests that *Khadira* is the most effective oral treatment for skin problems, while *Aragwadha* is best for local application.

Cosmetic Herbs in Ayurveda

Acharya *Charaka* classified several herbs depending on their benefits, such as *Varnya* (complexion-promoting), *Keshya* (hair growth-promoting), *Kushtaghna* (anti-dermatosis), *Vayasthapana* (rejuvenating), etc., all of which contribute to improving both physical and mental beauty. Some examples include:

- *Varnya Gana* – *Candana* (*Santalum album*), *Punnaga* (*Calophyllum inophyllum*), *Padmaka* (*Prunus cerasoides*), *Usira* (*Vetiveria zizanoides*), *Madhuka* (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), *Manjistha* (*Rubia cordifolia*), *Sariva* (*Hemidesmus indicus*), *Payasya* (*Ipomoea paniculata*), *Sita* (white variety of *Cynodon dactylon*) and *Lata* (black variety of *Cynodon dactylon*).

- *Kandughna Gana* includes *Chandana* (*Santalum album*), *Nalada* (*Nardostachys jatamarsi*), *Aragvadha* (*Cassia fistula*), *Naktamala* (*Pongamia pinnata*), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica*), *Kutaja* (*Holarrhena antidysenterica*), *Sarsapa* (*Brassica nigra*), *Madhuka* (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), *Daruharidra* (*Berberis aristata*), and others.

Acharya Sushruta categorised cosmetic medicines as *Lodhradigana*, *Arkadigana*, and *Eladigana*. He also described numerous *Kshudraroga*, *Lepas*, oils, and pharmaceutical compositions.

Cosmetic surgery practice

Susrutacharya, known as the “Father of Surgery,” made great advances to cosmetology. *Sushruta*, the first author to explain plastic and reconstructive surgery, discusses pharmacological and non-surgical treatments for skin, hair, ear, and nose issues. Wound management involves 60 measures (*Shashti upakrama*). *Sushruta* cites cosmetic therapies such as *pandukarma*, which uses whitening techniques to treat hyperpigmented scars.

- *Pandukarma*, apply *Bhallataka* (*Samecarpus anacardium*) taila and *Bhasma* (ash) from domestic and marshy animal hooves topically.
- *Krishnakarma* is a hypopigmentation treatment that darkens the skin. After soaking *Rohini phala* in goat milk for seven days, it is used as a paste externally.
- *Romasanjanana*: Regrowth of hair. *Lepa* is a paste formed from *Hastidanta masi*, *Rasanjana*, and goat milk. *Kasisa*, *Naktamala pallava* triturated with *Kapitha Rasa* is recommended for *roanjananammas*.
- *Romashatana*: This includes depilation techniques. *Sushruta* suggests using *Kshura* (razor), *Kartari* (scissors), or *Samdamsha yantra* (nasal forceps) for *Romashatana*. *Shankhabhasma* (two parts) and *Haratala* (one part) are triturated in *Kanji* and used in *Romashatanam*.

Advantages of Ayurvedic Cosmeceuticals

- Reduces skin irritation and provides safety.
- Because they are suitable, ayurvedic cosmetics encourage patient compliance.
- Unwanted side effects and chemical reactions are absent from natural products.
- acts at the cellular level, enhances regular processes, is readily absorbed, and has restorative qualities.
- When applied directly to sunburn, natural fragrances provide a pleasant sensation with calming and soothing benefits.
- Alopecia, dark circles, dandruff, scars, pigmented skin, accelerated ageing, and skin sensitivity are among the ailments that can be treated with Ayurvedic beauty products.^[17-19]

CONCLUSION

Cosmetology encompasses more than just attractive skin and hair, but also physical, mental, and social aspects. *Ayurveda*, unlike modern cosmetology, emphasises healthy beauty through internal ideas like as *Samaagni*,

Pathyahara, *Dinacharya*, and *Rithucharya*, rather than just exterior procedures. Although there are risks and restrictions to modern cosmetology and cosmetic surgery, technology has advanced to the point where individuals may now purchase personalised beauty products. *Ayurveda* can benefit society by providing natural, safe, effective, and holistic cosmetology treatments. *Ayurvedic* remedies address both physical and aesthetic difficulties.

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